

Religion among the tribes of India with special reference to Rangfraa religion among the Tangsas of Arunachal Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

India's tribal communities practice diverse indigenous religions rooted with animism, ancestor worship, and nature spirits that often blends with Hinduism or Christianity amid modernization. The Rangfraa faith among Arunachal Pradesh's Tangsa tribe exemplifies a 1990s revivalist movement, with restructuring traditional shamanistic beliefs into a monistic system honoring the supreme spirit Rangfraa to counter conversions and preserve identity. The aim of this paper is to examine the diversity of tribal religions in India, highlighting animism and regional variations along with it also try to analyze Rangfraa's origins, beliefs and practices like temple worship and festivals among Tangsa sub-tribes and who to assess Rangfraism's role in cultural revival, superstition reform, and identity assertion against proselytization.

This study will employs a qualitative approach combining ethnographic analysis, secondary literature review, and fieldwork insights. Key methods that include review of anthropological texts on tribal religions, examination of Rangfraa-specific sources like folklore songs and temple records, and case studies from Changlang district drawing on participant observation, interviews with Rangfraites and shamans (Keychus) and focuses on historical evolution and contemporary practices.

Key Words- Tribal religions, Animism, Rangfraa, Tangsa tribe, Arunachal Pradesh, Indigenous revival, Cultural identity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Religion as a symbolic system refers to the interpretation of religion through the lens of symbols, rituals, myths, and other forms of symbolic expression. The perspective is often associated with scholars such as Clifford Geertz and Mary Douglas, views religion as a complex system of mean-making that shapes individuals' understanding of the world and their place within it. Geertz defined religion as historically transmitted pattern of meaning embodied in symbols and a system of inherited conceptions expressed in symbolic forms by means of which men communicate, perpetuate and develop their knowledge about and attitudes towards life. He also tried to articulate the function of religious symbols how sacred symbols function within the cultural context that religion and religious activity are shaped by culture and it is important to approach to religion as being an integral element of culture itself.

Geertz defined "religion as system which acts to establish powerful, pervasive, and long lasting moods and motivations in men by formulating conceptions of a general order of existence and clothing these conceptions with such an aura of factuality that the moods and motivations seem uniquely realistic".

He also defined symbol as an object, act, event, quality or relation which serves as vehicle for a conception is the symbol. Symbols are central to religious expression, serving as vehicles for conveying complex meanings and values. Religious symbols can take various forms, including images, objects, rituals, gestures, and words. They represent abstract concepts, spiritual truths, and collective beliefs within religious traditions. Symbols are typically public, observable, concrete embodiments of ideas, attitudes, judgment, longings or beliefs.

Sacred symbols establish powerful, pervasive and long lasting moods and motivation in people. symbols are powerful they not only invoke deep moral sentiments concerning how the world should be but it also shape human behavior and influence how human beings interpret reality.

The religious symbol system also formulates conceptions of general order which they form a part of the worldview that shares unquestioned assumptions about the world and how it works. Most of the group's accept symbolic interpretation of the world as if they were real. Religion also provides a framework for making sense of the world and to interpret human experiences in symbolic terms. Symbols within religious traditions carry layers of meaning that go beyond the literal significance, often evoking emotions, beliefs, and cultural values shared by believers.

Mary Douglas has been described by Adam Kuper as one of the leaders of the new British 'Structuralism'. She is concerned with anomalies which imply loss of purity and therefore a source of danger. In her study *Natural Symbols* (1970), she holds that society as an entity is expressed by rituals symbolism.

Mary Douglas (1966, 1970) argues that the origins of symbolization are related to social structure in general and to processes of human body in particular. Douglas (1970) explores the cosmology of various societies and their relations with the corresponding bodily symbols. Human body is used to express the experiences of social relations. We present our body in different postures and angles, depending upon the situation whether it is formal or informal. According to Douglas (1970) experienced social relations are structured in two ways: group and the grid. Group is a bounded social unit whereas grid indicates a person-to-person relationship on an ego-centered basis.

2. Theories of Religion:

In the theories of the origin of religion the thinkers consider religion as an empirical entity that can traced historically and mapped geographically. All the religions are the human creations whose history is part of human culture. They were created to give people a feeling of security in an insecure world and a feeling of control over the environment where there was little control.

2.1 Naturalistic origin of Religion

From the enlightenment onwards there has been an attempt to study religion naturalistically. Why do people in societies seem to believe in the existence of invisible supernatural beings that influence human life for good or ill and whom it is advisable to pray? The Naturalistic theory of the origin of religion is Ernst Haeckel, a scientist turn philosopher. He expressed his conviction that the discoveries of 19th century science bring about solution of the enigmas which are the perplexed mankind through the centuries. He called his system a 'monism' (a theory or doctrine that denies the existence of duality in a particular sphere, such as that between matter

and mind, or God and the world). Haeckel tried to combine his activities to promote Darwinism with popularization of his own 'monism'. He presented 'monism' as a scientific movement which based on Darwinism and which aimed to free science from the bonds of "dualistic" Christianity, "metaphysics" and all "irrationality" (Holt, 1971). According to him in course of evolution the rudimentary psychical character of substance gradually advances to consciousness which according to him is purely natural phenomenon. Monism implies that there is no matter without spirit or energy and no spirit without matter. The idea of Monism is based on science and it solves through the riddles of existence. It gives negative answers to the traditional problems of God, freedom and immortality. The idea of God, freedom and immortality are based on mistaken dualism. In the monistic deterministic cosmos there is no room for the immortality of the soul or the freedom of the will.

2.2 Anthropological Origin of Religion:

The Naturalistic interpretation of religion gained support from the Anthropologist like Edward Burnett Taylor, James Frazer and Salmon Reinach. E.B. Taylor made two assumptions that human culture including knowledge, art, and religion, custom has its own law which can be studied scientifically. Secondly, the various grade of culture found in human race can exhibit as stages of development and evolution.

E.B. Taylor main contribution was the theory of Animism i.e. belief in the spiritual beings which confront with the phenomena such as death, sleep, dreams which primitive man account for them in terms of a spirit having the rank of powerful deities. According to him we have to begin the religion with the belief in spiritual beings at minimum condition. The superiority of the higher religion consists in the moral ideas which mostly lack in primitive religion and moral ideas turned out to be the abiding fruit of animism.

James George Frazer expressed his thought about religion and magic in his book "The Golden Bough". As in common language we know that magic is special kind of miracle by which people can be attracted or attracted towards them. Frazer believed that witchcraft have prevalent in the first place. It is estimated that man must have use magic first to gain control over primitive human nature to fulfill his purposes. When he saw that many time that magic failed and he cannot achieve his objectives by magic he realized that the supernatural power cannot be control by man through magic.

When such situation arises people started to worship and pray, through which religion originates. According to Frazer unsuccessful witchcraft led man to follow religion. It can say that religion is the result of the attitude defeated by nature. Frazer put forward two situations in the origin of religion (1) the idea of Witchcraft (2) the worship of supernatural power when magic fails. Worship begins which laid the foundation of religion.

Salomon Reinach who was an anthropologist largely devoted to the investigation of religion. He wants to show religion as natural phenomenon. And also described magic as "the strategy of animism," and he based his definition of religion on the Latin word *religio*, calling it "a sum of scruples which impede the free exercise of our faculties". With this definition he wants to eliminate from religion the concept of God, Spiritual beings. These scruples have arised from the irrational taboos of primitive societies where they were associated with an animistic view of the world. Thus he believed that human progress takes place through the gradual secularizing of

elements which are originally all enveloped in the sphere of Animistic beliefs. This process takes place not only in the transformation of taboos into moral rules but also helps in the development of science out of magic.

2.3 Social origin of Religion:

In the work of Emile Durkheim the theory of origin of religion gets a sociological importance. He viewed religion not as a sociological theory but completely a philosophy known as sociological positivism. According to him the character of primitive religion is best seen not in animism but in totemism which he considered as the fundamental and primitive form of religion. The totem is for the group that is sacred and the basis for the distinction of sacred and profane and takes the essence of religion. Totemisms as the type of religion were he concludes that religion is to be understood as a social phenomenon. Religion serves the needs of the society in which it is practiced and the object of cult that figure about the particular mythology. The idea of primitive religion suffered from the defect of one sided concentration upon religious belief. He claimed that religion is eternal.

2.4 Functional theories of Religion

Malinowski and Redcliffe Brown have given the functional explanation of primitive religion. He point about function explanation of the religion with reference to Trobriand Islanders that religion is intimately connected with various emotional states which are state of tension. For ex. The magical and religious practices centre round the fishing expeditions. These are outcome of the state of fear which possible disaster on the seas give rises to. In the same way the hate, greed, anger and love rise in man's life in different situations. These situations create stresses and strain and exist over a long time. Human being start to act in individual and normal action is not possible in the emotional state of mind. In such situation religion is made use of it to purge the human mind of its stress and strain. In other word we can say that religion function to bring about readjustment between man and supernatural in upset states of existence.

Redcliff Brown takes a different stand on functional theory of religion he said that religion dies not function under the state of fear and other emotional strains from the human minds but to instill sense of dependence in it. He point out that ultimate survival of group is more important than that of individuals. If individual make a sacrifice it is his interest to do so because without social survival individual survival is not possible. If individual does not realize and seeks to perform his action then there will be utter confusion and chaos with no possible organized activity. Adherence to norms of behavior is essential in terms of social survival and it is fear of supernatural control and punishment and to anticipate the support of social approval that brings about adherence. The function of religion is to create twofold feelings of dependence on society and thereby obtain the individuals occurrence with the social norms that ultimately aim at social survival. The function of religion is the contribution it makes to the total activity which is designed to perpetuate the society.

Thus we can say that Malinowski and Redcliff Brown have different views on function of religion on society but one thing that seem to common is that both thought about individual's importance in the society and society to individuals. Radcliff Brown and Malinowski's sociological explanation are derived from Durkheim's theory of religion. The religious notion

are born and conceived from social group through festivals and social gathering. Social life on occasions is intense and impresses the human mind which is transcendentalism and omnipotence of the group. Religion is the recognition of the superiority, moral and physical of the social group over individual.

Durkheim defined religion through beliefs and rites, the belief constitute the static part of religion and rites through dynamic part. In religion we have sacred beliefs, beliefs which refer to Gods and deities who are actually symbolic of society. These beliefs are put into practice by performance of rites. Profane beliefs and practices are not sacred and don not form a part of religion, they are magic.

The tribal world represents the Supreme Being or Sing Bonga or the Bhagwan as the creator of the Earth and the mankind. There are myths among the tribal about the universe. It explains a ceremony or the cult as why the tribal people believe in the existence of Myths as there are many romantic or heroic story of the some historical person or figure which finally give the tribal group their clan identity or family God.

The Tribal India has a rich stock of tribal myths and legends and sacred occasions that explain about the Myth. The clans, the village, the place all have something mythological behind. The Saoras believe that Kittung is the creator of the Earth and the man. It was believed that he was destroyer of all living creature expecting a male or a female. (Elwin, 1955). The new world was made in a variety of ways according to different tribal myths. The Munda myths explain that it was Sing Bonga who brooded over water and the first beings born were a kachua or tortoises, a karakom or crab and a lended or leech. The stories of the existence of tribal group or clan from different animals will continue out of this came a boy and girl and there were the progenitors of the Horo Honko the sons of men.

If we talk about the religion of tribal India is basically Hindu. It is well known that Hinduism is the product of many cultures. Every kind of religious act from sacrifices of the Vedic Aryans to the rituals of the primitive people can be observed in the main body of the Hindu Religion. 1961 census present a clear picture of the tribal religion in India. The tribal have altogether 59 religions in which they believe. As many of the tribal religions not yet recognised. According to 1961 census report 89.39 %of tribal people follow Hindu religion, 5.53% follow Christianity, a very negligible percentage follow Buddhism (0.89%), Islam (0.21%), Jainism, Sikhism and Zoroastrianism(all three together 0.34%). About 4.19% of the tribal people follow distinct Adivasi religion of their own. The region wise distribution of religion found that Hindus are found only in four regions expects the south India i.e. Andaman and Nicobar Island and Lakshadweep which are far from the mainland and located in the Bay of Bengal and the Arabian Sea. Almost 99% of the tribals of Western India respectively Rajasthan, Gujarat and Maharashtra, south India like Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu and in middle India states like Madhya Pradesh are Hindus. In Orissa, West Bengal and Kerala the strength of Hindu Tribal are more than 90%.

Tribals in the most parts of western and central regions includes Bihar and part of Tripura in the North eastern regions including Bihar and part of Tripura in the north eastern Himalayan region have embraced Hinduism. Christians are found among the scheduled tribes in Assam, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Manipur and Mizoram area of the North eastern Himalaya and constitute less than fifty per cent of the tribal population of the region. In south India particularly in Kerala

4.75% of the tribal population whereas in Andaman and Nicobar Islands 74.31% tribal population are Christians. Buddhism among the tribes is concentrated in some part of Assam, Tripura, West Bengal and Himachal Pradesh. Muslims are there among tribes of the Lakshadweep Island. Himachal Pradesh had 3.4%, West Bengal had 2.75% and Maharashtra had 0.9% of the Muslim population.

The form of religion practised by the Tribals throughout India is thus more or less, Hindu. Hutton in his 1931 Census Report found it difficult to draw a line of distinction between Hinduism and the tribal religion and the latter presents a kind of surplus materials which has not been built into temple of Hinduism. Baines considered the distinction between the tribal people who were Hinduised and those that followed their tribal form of religion as futile. Gait said that it is difficult to say at what stage a man should be considered as Hindu. As it is difficult to distinguish a Hindu from Animist. According to Ghurye (1963) the tribal religion is a backward form of Hindu religion. Verrier Elwin (1944) pointed out that Religion of the tribal people in India had a close affinity with the Saivite section of Hinduism and point out the distinction between tribal religion and Hinduism was meaningless. The tribal people are always willing to worship a few Gods by doing so they can gain some material or social advantage. Elwin on other hand also pointed out that Hindu had no objection to include multi God pantheon a few tribal Gods. In order to judge the statement put forward by Elwin, D.N Majumdar (1961) opined that the tribal religion represent "Marginal religion" a no –man's land between magic and religion, between pseudo science and science.

Gonds religious lives are different from that of lower Hindu castes. In most part of tribal India the tribesmen had adopted their ancient belief and practices more or less from those of popular Hinduism by adopting different names for their deities and by indifference they show in respect of food, drink or performances.

Features of Tribal Religion

1. Nature of belief in supernatural powers.

1. Animism- Among the sacred beliefs the faith in spirits is most common with the tribal and the Animism. The animistic belief is universal features of the religion among the tribal people. Animals, plants, trees, ponds, rivers, stones, hills or mountain all are the adobes of spirits. The whole neighbourhood whether village or forest in which the tribal people lives have full of spirits. The Major tribes like the Santhal, Munda or Oraon or minor tribes like the Birhor, Chenchu or the forest hunting tribes of South India, the whole world is the full of spirits.

In middle India, the Santhals and Oraons believe in the presence of the souls of their own dead whom they worship at Majhiye Than. Among the Korwas of Mirzapur, as D.N. Majumdar (1961) states that the spirits presiding over crops, another over rainfall, still another over cattle and number of spirits are there which dictate the attitude of the Korwas to their neighbours, to the tribal priest, to the headman and to the general affairs of the tribe.

In north eastern Himalaya among the Mikirs the localities with impressive mountains, waterfalls, deep pools and rivers, great boulders etc., have assigned to them gods which are supposed to be interested in the affairs of men and have to be placated by sacrifices. The belief in the incarnation existed in the naming of the offspring. They generally name their children after the dead relatives because it believes that dead

come back to the world. The Garos believe in the existence of spirit in man which after death spends time in another sphere before he is incarnated. Among the Jaintiyas it was believe that when one falls ill their offer prayers to the ancestor to drive out evil spirit from the body. In the same way Mizos also believe in the existence of other worlds where in after death the spirits lives. The Nagas move around their village with big stone with the belief that spirits exist in the stone after dead.

In western India the Bhils believe in the survival of the dead and the soul continues to exist as a spirits. Among the Bhils they have numerous nature spirits like spirits of hills, streams and forest and the band of punitive and malevolent spirit. The tribe of Maharashtra like Varlis have a great influence on ancestor spirits. If anyone fall ill or tragic accident occurs they attribute it to the wrath of some God or to the act of a spirit or a witch. Vir is the ancestor God of Varlis. The Thakurs had Vir as their ancestor God.

Similarly in South India, the Malayarayans in Kerala observe some stones as symbols of deities. The dead ancestor in the form of deity goes on to protect his family. The Todas of the Nilgiri believe in the ancestral worships. They observe two death ceremonies one green and other dry. Buffaloes are beaten to death to accompany and live with the spirits of the dead Toda. The Muthuvans, Paliyans, Ullatans are the tribes of South India that makes a offerings to the Spirits of particular local hills or other awe- inspring natural objects.

2. Bongaism- D.N Majumdar (1961) stated that the animistic beliefs of the Tribals based on malevolent spirits and powers which influence the destiny of men. To discard the idea of the forms of religion among the primitive people, he opined that the tribal religion in India stands on the theory of Bongaism but did not propound with the view to make any hypothesis about the root of the primitive religion. The religious beliefs among the Ho, Munda and others tribes of the Chhotanagpur give ample indications of the strong belief in one particular cluster of Bonga. Bonga are rightly being called the Indian parallel of the Malenasian term "Mana".

Bonga was conceived by the Ho as the power that pervades all spaces. It was indefinite and impersonal to start with. That's way it was believed to take any shape or form. The power gives life to all animals and plants, it encourages the growth in plants, and it brings down rain, storm, hail, flood and cold. It kills and destroys evils, stops epidemics, cures diseases, gives current to rivers, venom to snakes and strength to tigers, bears and wolves. Among the Hos it was reveal that when the curiosity of a child was aroused by any mechanical contrivance however simple or crude, like a cycle, rail engine, plane etc, it is immediately satisfied by calling of Bonga. D.N. Majumdar (1961) understand Bonga as the father or any adult of his tribe does, it gives him a vague idea about the power, the nature of which he does not know nor would the adult of his tribe worry about.

According to Vidyarthi (1963) among the Maler community, every child, adult and old, every commoner and specialist, had some sort of conception in his mind about the spirit and supernatural worlds which he calls by the common term Gossaiyan. The term Gossaiyan is household word and is used to denote a group spirits that believed to guide their destiny and male children are instructed about the Gossaiyan. Among the Birhors the idea of Bir was present. They are number of Birs present and have different responsibility. Hanuman Bir being the supreme and others are hunters (wolf)

- Bir, Bagh (tiger), Bir, Bhal (bear) bir, Sundar (hunting) Bir and sons of the Birs. The Birs protect the Birhors in different way and always conscious in the presence of Birs.
3. Naturalism- Worship of nature is the other form of belief that prevails among the tribes. Sun, Moon and Earth are considered as creator and supreme power. The Santhal, Mundas, Hos, Malers and Birhors tribal community of Bihar identify Sun as Sing Bonga i.e. supreme God. The Santhals equate Dharmesh, the supreme deity, with sun and regarded as husband of Dharti Mata and mother Earth. The Earth, the Sun, the Fire and Water are regarded as deities, the great supernatural beings and are believed in by the Bondos of Orissa. For the Bondos of Orissa the sun was the creator. In the Himalayan region, the Garos consider the sun, the moon and the stars as spirits are placed as Creator and ruling the region. Along with the Garos, the Kacharis also believe that Earth is the Creator.
In South India the Todas and Koyas revere the Sun. The Muthuvans, Uralis and Kanikkars of Kerala recognize the sun as their God. The Muthuvans worship the sun in the morning. The Uralis take the sun as the creator, the Kanikkars know the Sun as Bhagavan.
 4. Totemism- Totemism was the common feature of the Indian tribal population and the most of them believe in their mysterious relation with some plants, besides animals. Totemism involves the belief that individuals or groups have a special relationship with particular totem, which serves as a symbolic representation of their clan, lineage or community. Totems are often believed to embody spiritual qualities or ancestral connections and associated with ancestral spirits or guardian beings, believed to offer protection, guidance and blessings to those who identify with them.
The Killi of Hos is their clans and each clan bears a totemic object which is sacred to them. The Santhal and the Kharia have a clan named after plants or animals or material objects. All the tribes are considered that the totemic plants or animals have helped or protected their respective ancestors.
 5. Ancestor Worship- the activities of ancestors are quite evident of the tribals and ancestor worship finds an important place in among the tribal people in their religious beliefs. They recognised that man's power is restricted and that he has access to limited areas but ancestor worship acquires powers of a far reaching and compulsive kind. They believe in the existence of ancestors and their interest and intervention in the worldly affairs. Vidyarthi (1963) consider ancestor worship an important aspect of the tribal religion.

3. Hinduisation of tribes during Ancient and Medieval Periods:

In the book Socio-economic characteristics of tribal communities that call Hindus themselves by Vinay Kumar Srivastava (2010) he mentioned about the religious exchanges with Hindus among the tribal community. Tribal people have a relationship with other religious streams as well as with local cults and sects. The interaction with majority of Hindu community as it noted that Hinduism is non proselytizing religion (Srinivas and Shah, 1968). The first mode of interaction between tribal people and Hindus is the process of religious borrowing or syncretism. The Tharu and the Khasa tribes of central Himalayan tribes in North India are good example that assimilated or hinduised tribes. They adopted Hindu caste names wearing the sacred thread, established social links with the local Rajputs and Brahmin groups, these tribal have tried to incorporate their identity with high caste Hindus.

Kosombi (1975) stated that tribal people tried to fuse into the general society with its own element of tribal features. N.K.Bose (1941) made a reference that tribes being absorbed into Hindu society. Some of the well known tribes like Bhils, Bhumji, Majhi all have accepted the ethos of caste structure and have absorbed Hindu way of life. Roy- Burman (1972) had classified tribes into following categories: - 1. Those incorporate in Hindu society, 2. Those positively oriented to Hindu Society, 3. Those negatively oriented 4. Those indifferent to Hindu society like Oraon and Santhals who have incorporated some traits of caste society and Hinduism but have retained their tribal status; negatively oriented tribes like some tribal communities of North East India who nurture alienation toward the mainstream society due to historical reasons and; indifferent tribes like in Arunachal Pradesh who are equally oriented towards Hinduism and Christianity. What Roy Burman identified is the perception of tribes toward the mainstream society. According to M.N. Srinivas the Hindu way of life should comprise the mainstream approach because caste and religion are two essential characteristics of mainstream culture. However, the criticism to this view came mainly from Roy Burman(1972) who opined that it would exclude the communities of North East India and others who are non-Hindus in the mainland.

Kosombi (1975) considered that the adoption of technology of Hindu society by the tribes took place under the prevalent system for the organization of production. He also said that tribes are drawn into the non competitive system because they find protection within it. Through sanskritisation tribes tried to absorb the Hindu way of life. Sinha (1962) point out that the state formation was the method through which the tribes adopt the Hindu way of life or Hinduisation took place. In the eastern India the Bauri of west Bengal accepted to observe the number of day of pollution for mourning wear the scared thread, go to pilgrimage and follow Vishnavism. They claim to be belonging to Brahmin group.

Scholars like N.K Bose and Mandelbaum were of the opinion that tribes are gradually becoming castes and this process is continuing since time immemorial. N.K. Bose conducted his ethnographic study on the Juangs at Pallahara in Orissa. The Juangs who were originally forest tribes were forced to migrate due to the forest policy adopted by the Orissa government in 1936. One group migrated to Pallahara and the other to Dhenkanal; the group to Pallahara adopted wheat cultivation and got absorbed into the local peasant caste community; while the group to Dhenkanal started making baskets and got absorbed into the local oil men caste. S.C. Dube had reported similar case among the Raj Gonds, Surajit Sinha among the Bhumij of West Benga, and by Mandelbaum on the Urali of Travancore.

The interaction between Hindu civilization and tribes has been continuing for centuries, if not millennia. However, the existence of tribal religion in India has remained out of contact with caste societies and Hinduism owing to both geographical and historical reasons. Thus among the tribes of North East India and elsewhere there might be similarities with the Hindu beliefs and practices, especially with regards to worshipping of nature and reverence for celestial bodies; nevertheless, to circumscribe these tribes within the Hindu fold basing on these characteristics would involve the politicization of religious identity, since it would require an imposition of the Vedic/Hindu worldview on these tribes, although most of these indigenous religions have developed according to their own geniuses. Importantly, the impact of world religions like Hinduism and Christianity has made the religious identity and affiliation more complex among the tribes giving rise to newer religious processes, dilemma and even religious tensions.

The spread of Hinduism in the tribal world follow two processes. First at local level, it exists alongside with folk religion and sort of blending between two religions. Second a scriptural form of more pure Hinduism is diffused by religious institution. In the first process the two different religious streams come into natural contact and negotiate the similarities and difference to chart the mutual coexistence. The second process is the concert effort to spread the values and lifestyles of the religion. Some of the Hindu organization tried to entre tribal areas to spread their faith with an explicit intent to encounter the impact of Christianity.

Missionaries were sent to different part of the country where tribes are inhabited, as most of the tribal people follow traditional tribal religion like Animism and Naturalism are replaced by one or the other denomination of Christianity. Schools were opened and English was opted as main language of instruction. Christianity was the sole vehicle of modernization. The neo-converts not only became a part of the Great Tradition of Christianity, but were also linked to the Great Tradition of the Western culture, English language that flourished as far superior and 'advanced' to the local culture. The fate of traditional material culture and styles of living was decided and they were to be 'preserved' as museum specimens.

The British policy towards the tribal had two major elements. Firstly it favored isolation of tribal areas from the mainstream society (Bhowmick 1980). The concept of excluded and partially excluded areas was introduced. The British tribal policy was political and colonial, the British administrators feared that if tribal people come in contact with the main stream society they would gain strength and might fight back against the Britisher. So with logical reasoning the Britisher thought to keep them isolate in both administratively and politically.

Secondly at the level of reform the British administration was interested in civilizing the tribal people. In an ethno-centric assessment, the tribal were viewed at par with stage of bestiality. The classical theory of evolution, which had gripped academic attention in late nineties and early twenties, had treated the 'contemporary primitives' as the remnants or survivals of the early stages of humanity, savagery and barbarism. In the words of Sir E.B. Tylor, these people inhabiting the hilly or forested terrain with sparse population and difficult communication were 'social fossils', a study of who would illuminate the prehistoric phases of human existence.

The impact of Christianity among the tribal people was started through process of the proselytization which was seen first in North East India among the Khasis Tribes of Meghalaya in 1813. Then it's also observed in Madhya Pradesh Bhil tribe and in Chotanagpur Oraons tribe. Missionary along with the co-operation of British Government started to convert people into Christianity.

In Bihar total one-tenth of the tribal population is Christian. The impact of Christianity has less covered in part western India Gujarat, Rajasthan and Maharashtra. And Major conversion was seen and reported from the south India. It was reported that Toda Tribes have converted about half of the population. Christianity has replaced original religion and loss of the faith from own religion. The Conversion has basically started because of the poor miserable condition of the tribes. They are very low and backward in terms of economically, they were exploited by the zamindars and upper caste. Upper caste people don't allow them to touch the water-well, untouchability were high.

Some tribes follow only one religion. However there are many tribes how follow more than one religion such as Hinduism, Christianity, Islam and other indigenous religion. In the spread of Christianity among the tribes of North East India is remarkable. Namely in the states of Manipur,

Nagaland, Mizoram and Meghalaya the followers of Christianity is much more in compare to other states of North East.

There has been a revival of traditional religion among the tribes. The most significantly manifest in Arunachal Pradesh where a religion named Donyi-polo was in rise. Consequently there has been a decline in the Hindu religion in Arunachal Pradesh. In Meghalaya about 27.75 % follow their own indigenous religion. Similarly in Bihar tribes were returning to what they called the pristine religion, the cult of sacred grove. Madhya Pradesh also witnesses the revival and consolidation of Gondi Dharma.

4. RELIGION IN NORTH EAST INDIA

North east is one of the most culturally diverse regions in India. North eastern India comprises eight states namely Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Nagaland, Manipur, Mizoram, Tripura and Meghalaya often known as seven sisters and Sikkim referred as brother to seven sisters. It is surrounded by Bhutan, Tibet, China, Myanmar, and Bangladesh and a long narrow passage in the west which connects the region with rest of India. It occupies an area of 255,000 sq km, it comprises above 7 % land mass of the total land mass of the India. It also has unique culture and traditions, different tribes have their own oral literature consisting of songs, and folklores, religion.

Arunachal Pradesh known as the Land of Rising Sun. It is situated on the North Eastern end of India. Geographically, it is the largest state of North East region. It became India's 24th state in December 1986. It is surrounded by Bhutan, China and Myanmar, and also by adjoining states of Assam and Nagaland. The people of Arunachal Pradesh speak more than 40 different languages and dialects, main tribal languages of Arunachal Pradesh are Adi, Bodo/Boro, Mikir, Mishmi, Monpa, Nishi/Dafla, Nocte, Tangsa and Wancho which mostly belonging to the Sino-Tibetan linguistic family specially the Tibeto-Burmese branch. The main religions are Buddhism Hinduism, Christianity and various other indigenous religions and other religion. According to 2011 census report around 54% people are Hindus, 17.34% are Christians, 1.01% is Buddhism 25.36% people are Muslims and 2.29% are the followers of indigenous religion.

Among all the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh the Tangsa tribe plays a very important role in socio religious identity of the tribal groups. Tangsa Migrant from Indo Tibetan Plateau who were initially animist and but later on convert to Christianity with the advent of missionaries mostly Baptist. There are thirty-two Sub-division in the Tangsa community. Tangsa Sub Groups such as Muklum, Longchang, Havi are gathered under the umbrella title of Tangsa, a term coined in 1956. The Tangsa are divided into two sections depending on their residence in India. The first groups of settlers are known as Tangwa while those who arrived later are known as Pangwa or Pangsa. There is a village in Burma that is directly related to Muklum and Havi, The Tangwa lived almost exclusively in Arunachal Pradesh and claimed a variety of them come from 'just over the border' to the Hukawang valley of Burma. The Tangsa people on the other hand have most of their villages on the Burmese side of the border where they are known as Ha Chat a northern branch of the Heimi. (Saul 2005).

The Tangsa group that arrived in India was the followers of Hinduism and Buddhism, when the American Baptist Missionaries arrived in North East India in the late 19th century most of the tribes of Nagaland, Manipur, Mizoram, and Arunachal Pradesh adopted the Christian religion. Along with other tribal communities, the Tangsa community also adopted the Christian religion.

The Tangsas of not only India but Myanmar also started to convert to Christianity from the 1950s to 1970s through a mutual contract between Tangsas of the two countries. Most of the Tangsa group who arrived in India have adopted Christianity, out of that few have not converted and still follow their old traditional beliefs, while few of them adopted Rangfraism a new religion based on traditional practices of the Tangsa. (Barkataki, 2015).

In the article “Best of all Worlds: Rangfraism: The New Institutionalized Religion of the Tangsa Community in Northeast India” (Barkataki, 2015) it was mentioned that the community’s understanding of the traditional religion is mostly guided by the following thumb of rules: “What is old is traditional”, what we did in the hills before moving down to the plains is traditional” and what we did before we converted to Christianity is traditional”. Most of the Tangsa used to believe in benevolent spirits like Wihu which protect and bring prosperity and also some malevolent spirits which cause illness and bring misfortune. Many Tangsa elite groups used the term Hindu to refer to their older traditional practices because like the Hindus the Tangsa also used to sacrifice animals. This inclusive nature of Hinduism among the Tangsa, claimed them to be Hindu and remained so till the 1970s when the Baptist missionaries arrived and the whole scenario of Northeast India changed. (Xaxa, 2005).

As Christianity made deep inroads among the Tribes of North east India like Tangsa community, the Tangsa became more aware of their proselytization and conversion activities, and the need to control it became imminent. There were parallel religious movements took place all over Arunachal. In the wake of the Christian conversions taking place in Arunachal, the questions on the significance and importance of protecting and preserving indigenous religious beliefs and practices had come to light, and new reformist movements generated taxonomies such as Donyi-Poloism, and Intayaism movement among the Adi tribes and Nishi tribes. In the same way Tangsa tribe also started religious movement called Rangfra movement, much like other reformist movements, stood as an exemplary measure towards recognition and representation of their traditional cultural heritage against the changing socio-economic landscape among the Tangsas.

As we all know that Tangsa is one of the major tribal groups of Arunachal Pradesh and Assam. They are scheduled Tribes as per the Constitution (Scheduled Tribes) Order, 1950 listed under ‘Other Naga Tribes’ of Arunachal Pradesh. But in 2018 a revised bill was passed in a union cabinet meeting under the Chairmanship of Prime Minister Narendra Modi namely, the Constitution (Scheduled Tribes) Order (Amendment) bill, 2018 where the Tangsa are listed under ‘Any Naga Tribes’ of Arunachal Pradesh. The word ‘Tangsa’ literally means “children of hills” or “people of high land” which cover 35 Trans Patkai ethnic groups. And it is an umbrella term used for the collection of small ethnic groups who had migrated to India from Myanmar, most of them within the last couple of centuries. In Myanmar, they are known as Tangshang. Sometimes the term Tangwa is also used which means “father of high land” and it is referred to the forefathers of Tangsa who wore loin cloths. The word Tang means “to sacrifice” because some groups of the Tangsa performed human sacrifice.

In Myanmar Tangsa are known as Rangpang, Pangmi and Heimi. Tangsa of both countries regards themselves as Naga Tribes. They had settled in the northeastern state of Assam in Tinsukia District and Arunachal Pradesh of Changlang District. They have inhabited the hills and the valleys of the wider areas in the Tirap River and the Burhi Dihing River up to Miao. They are

spread in both the Changlang and the Miao subdivisions. Tangsa of Myanmar and India have a good relationship with each other, though they have linguistic, religious, and cultural differences.

In the article “Rangfra movement: A genius to indigenous” in Organiser: Voice of Nation it mention about the Tangsa Migrant from Indo Tibetan Plateau who are initially animist and many have convert to Christianity with the advent of missionaries mostly Baptist. In the late 1990s inspired by the nationalist movement some Tangsa leader like Latsam Khimun an engineer by profession set up a society for reforms but realised that religious tenor required. Latsam Khimun had written several holy books that codify the religion. It seen that they picked up the idea and moral lesson from all over but affirm that Rangfraism is the part of Hindu fold. L.Khimun said that “As per our definition all those who are willing to die and live for the Hindustan are Hindus. Those who are anti Hindu or anti national, they criticise Rangfraites. Especially the Christians, I shall openly”. His holy books speak of the need to reconvert from Christian. There has been violence on the occasions in the state between Christian Tribals and revivalist groups. The movement brought about radical changes in the lives of the tribal people that enable them to reconnect with the cultural roots.

Rangfra movement is not an isolated phenomenon just like Donyi-Polo movement as new religious identity that had spread among the Abo tani groups and in the same way the Intayism among the Idu Mishimi tribes, the cult or Rangfra religion spread across the Tirap and Changlang district of Arunachal Pradesh.

Latsam Khimun played an important role in rejuvenating Rangfraasim a faith of the Tangsa tribal in the Arunachal Pradesh who was initially animist by nature. With Rangfrasim many tribal people came back to their indigenous faith and believe.

In mid of 1990s Rangfraa movement was started by professional educated Tangsa doctor, engineer and civil servant led by the charismatic Latsam khimhum, a civil engineer by profession and government employee. They saw the danger of losing the traditional culture and values of the community by converting into Christianity. Since moving down from the hills and giving up the traditional beliefs system had become redundant and obsolete.

Rangfraism is the name given for a revivalist movement of Tangsa traditional spirituality or we can say that Rangfraism as reformed cult of the Tangsa. The intention was “to give an alternative form of religious belief to those who were neither following the Christian beliefs nor the traditional ways”. The interesting aspect of the Rangfraa was to construct a Hindu deity look a likes. Thus Rangfraa has a Shiva like form idol with Mongoloid White face.

In the Rangfraism the practices of treating illness via divination and expensive sacrifices has been replaced by prayer, fasting and healing. Instead of sacrifices they offer flowers and agarbatti (incence).

As Tangsa used to spend a lot of money and energy trying to appease the malevolent spirits who they believed caused illness and misfortune. This was one of the reason were most of the tangsa got attracted towards the Christianity. Another reason for the conversion was that they had no name to traditional practices. But they used the term Rangfraa which literally means “God of skies”. So Rangfraa was chosen as the name of the New God and the Rangfraa Faith Promotion Society was formed in 1995. Firstly the aim the new religion was first to promote, preserve and protect what they perceived as traditional culture and secondly, to stop the strong wave of conversion to Christianity. To achieve this they decided on a two pronged reform of their traditional system: 1. to discard most of the obsolete and unscientific superstitions and taboo of

the old system. 2. To incorporate elements from other world religion this could make their religion more attractive to its followers.

Tangsa people decided to institutionalize their religion by setting up places of worship called Rang-som-hum (prayer house). The prayer house in New Changlang town of Arunachal Pradesh was designed by Latsam Khimhun himself. The design of the prayer house incorporates architectural elements from places of worships of four world religion- the central shrine with idol is borrowed from Hindu temple, the hall like building resembles a church, the round dome is taken from the Muslim Mosque and the crowning turret with glass windows recalls a Buddhist Pogoda. On 4th November 1997 the first idol of Rangfraa was installed in the prayer house at New Changlang. Prayer services (Rongsom) are held on Sunday, Wednesday and Saturday. The Rongsom means the combination of Romrom (rituals) and Rangtam (prayer). The service begins with the mass prayer followed by the singing of devotional songs. The service held in a mixture of language whereas the hymns and music is set by Latsam Khimhun in Muklom or Longchang languages. Latsam Khimhun the founder of Rangfraa religion said that Rangfraism and old practices of the religion has a relationship in three aspects: 1. the religious aspect which was not there before and has been added, 2. the cultural practices which has been kept completely intact, 3. The bad social practices which has been eliminated.

The double word Rang fraa was believed to embody the twin aspects of power (rang) through miracles and healing as well as that of wisdom and knowledge (fraa) that Rangfraa embodied. The religious component is structured along two lines: the Rang line represented by the Keychus (literally means "pure ones" mostly young girls who supposedly get possessed by the spirit of Rangfraa during a prayer service and acquire powers to heal and prophesy). The Rang side is female, the fraa side is male, together Rangfraa is complete. Since the Buddha is also called Phraa or fraa, so Buddhism is Fraa-ism, hence Buddhism according to Latsam Khimhun contained in Rangfraism. The system of initiation into Rangfraism and the advance through several stages to higher levels of moral and spiritual perfection similar to the Buddhist Path. However the Rang (power) aspect in Rangfraism tends more towards the Hindu aspects of Shakti (power and energy).

According to the new religion of the Tangsa community the cultural practices followed in Rangfraa are part of people identity. There was an internal contradiction from many outsiders, as most of the leaders of the Rangfraa movement look it as process of rationalizing their cultural and economic practices and claim that the traditional practices of Tangsa are feasible in today's world for which it need to be retained and modified. Some practices of Rangfraa are similar to Christianity like the practices of reading holy book on Sunday. The Baptism can be considered to be similar to initiation in Rangfraism. The marriage system that followed in Rangfarism is quite similar to Christianity. As it can be internalized that the Christian and the Rangfraa service impart a sense of fraternity and solidarity to the village community. It is clear that Rangfraa had adopted most of the ideology from the Christianity to keep the followers within the fold. We can say that Rangfraism is an attempt to stop the wave of Christian conversion. In one of the book it was found that Rangfraa society goes far to appeal to all those who converted to Christianity to adopt Rangfraism, there even set a procedure for reconversion. Using the slogan "Loss of culture is loss of identity". The Rangfra society leaders have tried to keep the Tangsa from converting to Christianity.

The Christian Tangsas refused to accept the claim made by Rangfraism and agree to view that institutionalization of Rangfraism is an interpolation of other religions. For Christian Tangsa the idea of Rangfraa was as mockery of the old traditions. Whereas Christian Tangsa viewed that

Rangfraism is certainly different from their old traditional belief system, but another 'Baptist Christian said that old man Tonku - wa in the mythical Rangfraa story was none other than the Noah of the Old Testament'. One thing it is clear that both Rangfraities and the Baptists has same ideological view and give advice to the people to keep the houses clean and to pray to God when people fall sick. From the above discussion it is clear that Rangfraa and Christianity are not different from each other.

In Rangfraa, idol worship was considered to be characteristic feature of Hinduism. So, many Rangfraism has criticized for introducing idol worship, but Rangfraa society member claim that they had no other option since they do not have symbol like cross (like Christianity). One thing it was clear that in Rangfraa houses the images of Shiva and Vishnu are placed and worship which they themselves cannot explain it. One think it was clear that the image of Rangfraa looks like tribal Shiva and the Keychus not only possessed the spirit of Rangfraa but also the spirits of Hindu Gods and Goddesses such as Shiva and Kali. Followers of Rangfraa made a comment that "Rangfraa and Shiva are same and they are like brothers".

We can say that Rangfraism is the offshoot of Hinduism and the fact is that main alter in the rangfraa prayer house was like that in a Hindu temple. Therefore it was not surprising that many practices of Hinduism are adopted by Rangfra besides idol worship, the uses of Diyas (oil lamp), and the uses of Agarbatti (incense) during the services, offering flowers, ringing of bells when entering the prayer house, the uses of tulsi leaves (basil leaves) are all essential Hindu temple rituals. Rangfraa society leaders have been accused of playing with the hands of Hindu Fundamentalist groups. Rangfra leader have said that there is no difference between the Janajati (ethnic Communities) and the Hindus. This fact was known to every Hindu from very beginning, so they never felt the need to convert the Janajati to Hinduism as they are already Hindu. The link with Hinduism was clear and since the primary aim of Rangfraa society leaders to stop conversion to Christianity which was labeled a foreign religion.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, religion among India's tribal communities, as a symbolic system of animism, Bongaism, totemism, ancestor worship, and nature reverence that articulated through scholars like Geertz and Douglas that serves as a dynamic framework for meaning-making, social cohesion, and worldview construction amid historical syncretism with Hinduism and Christianity. Theories from naturalistic (Haeckel), anthropological (Tylor, Frazer), social (Durkheim), and functional (Malinowski, Radcliffe-Brown) perspectives underscore religion's evolution from primitive responses to existential uncertainties into adaptive institutions, exemplified by features like sacred groves and totemic clans. The Rangfraa faith among Arunachal Pradesh's Tangsa tribe epitomizes contemporary revivalism, countering proselytization through monistic restructuring of shamanistic symbols, rituals, and myths, while broader Hinduisation, colonial isolation, missionary impacts, and recent indigenous movements like Donyi-Polo and Gondi Dharma highlight tribal religions' resilience in negotiating identity, purity, and modernity. Northeast India's cultural mosaic, exemplified by Arunachal Pradesh's Tangsa tribe amid the region's eight states and over 200 ethnic groups, underscores the dynamic interplay of indigenous animism, missionary-driven Christianity, and revivalist movements like Rangfraism. Initiated in the mid-1990s by leaders such as Latsam Khimun, Rangfraa restructured Tangsa shamanistic traditions discarding costly sacrifices and superstitions while incorporating Hindu idols, Christian services, Buddhist ethics, and Islamic architecture into a monistic faith venerating the supreme sky god Rangfraa, complete with prayer houses (Rang-som-hum),

Keychus healers, and reconversion appeals to halt Baptist conversions. This adaptive reform not only preserves Tangsa sub-tribal identity, folklore, and festivals across Changlang and Myanmar borders but also models ethnic resilience, fostering unity and cultural pride against globalization and proselytization in India's diverse tribal landscape.

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